

**FAKULTA
JADERNÁ
A FYZIKÁLNĚ
INŽENÝRSKÁ
ČVUT V PRAZE**

UNIVERZITA KARLOVA
Přírodovědecká fakulta

Reference areas for unmanned aerial radiometric survey

**Czech Technical University in Prague,
Faculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering
Charles University, Faculty of Sciences**

Contact:

RNDr. Ondřej Šálek, PhD., ondrej.salek@natur.cuni.cz
Ing. Václav Štěpán, PhD., vaclav.stepan@jfji.cvut.cz

This work is co-financed from the state budget by the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic and Ministry of the Environment under the Environment for life Programme within the project SS06010467.

Introduction

In the last decade, the use of unmanned aerial systems (UAS) for radiometric surveys has expanded significantly. The methodology for measurement, calibration, and data processing, which has been developed in detail for conventional manned aerial gamma spectrometry surveys, is only partially applicable to UAS. Methodological procedures for UAS radiometric measurements are currently developing rapidly and have not yet reached a standardized form. Nevertheless, the correctness of calibration and data processing is a fundamental attribute of radiometric data, ensuring quantitative comparability between different regions, authors, and detection systems.

Four reference sites were established for the experimental verification of the accuracy of methodological procedures and for comparing the quantitative results of different detection systems under real conditions, specifically to assess concentrations of natural radionuclides (potassium, uranium, thorium), and fallout ^{137}Cs . These reference sites are now available for national and international group inter-comparison measurements.

The reference sites represent a natural standard of the gamma radiation field that is subject to temporal variations. Therefore, the use of reference sites for the standardization of radiometric data from unmanned systems is designed as a comparative measurement among a group of participants, with the option to include corrections for environmental parameters. Radionuclide concentrations obtained by laboratory gammaspectrometric analysis of dry soil samples are available as baseline.

As part of the comparative measurement, the current state of the reference site is determined through a ground-based gamma spectrometric survey, soil moisture measurements, and monitoring of airborne radon using continuous monitor. These tasks are carried out by the reference site administrators on the day of the comparison measurements.

Fundamental properties of the reference sites

Geology

The reference sites were established on geological units with an increased abundance of one of the four radionuclides of interest (K, U, Th, and ^{137}Cs) and with an elevated ratio of this radionuclide relative to the others. The aim is to maximize the accuracy of determining each target element.

Radionuclide homogeneity

Sites with a homogeneous spatial distribution of the radionuclide of interest were selected.

Flat geometry

Reference sites cannot be perfectly flat. Areas with the flattest possible surface were selected; a slight and uniform slope is acceptable.

Vegetation

Vegetation at the sites consists only of grass, without trees or shrubs. The sites contains no arable land.

UAS operation with minimal administrative requirements

The sites are selected to allow operation of UAS under EASA Open A3 category. For systems flying operating in the EASA Specific category, CTU will provide assistance in communication with the Civil Aviation Authority of the Czech Republic.

Accessibility

Access to the land is ensured through agreements concluded with Czech Technical University in Prague and Charles University, who act as administrators of the reference sites and facilitate site access for other participants within the framework of the inter-comparison measurements.

Characteristics of the Reference Sites

Potassium Reference Site–Zbytiny

The reference site is located within the granulites, which are characterized by an increased ratio of potassium relative to other natural radionuclides. The average potassium content at the reference site is 2.5 %, while the uranium and thorium contents are very low—1.5 ppm U and 3.9 ppm Th. A map showing the location of the reference sites is presented in Fig. 1. An orthophoto with the site location is shown in Fig. 2a.

Uranium Reference Site–Kunžak

The reference site is located in an area with an elevated U/Th ratio, caused by the relatively low thorium content typical of this granite. The average uranium content at the reference site is 4.7 ppm eU, while thorium and potassium contents are 10.0 ppm eTh and 2.9 % K, respectively.

Gamma-ray energies from the uranium decay series are generally less represented in the natural gamma-ray spectrum than those from potassium and the thorium series. Uranium series gamma radiation overlaps with the higher-energy gamma rays of the thorium series, so the accuracy of uranium concentration determination increases in areas with a higher U/Th ratio. An orthophoto showing the site location is presented in Fig. 2b.

Thorium Reference Site–Slavoňov

The reference site lithologically consists of melasyenite, which is characterized by significant enrichment in incompatible elements, including natural radionuclides, making it one of the most radioactive rocks in the Bohemian Massif. The average thorium content at the reference site is 24.9 ppm eTh, while uranium and potassium contents are 6.5 ppm eU and 3.0 % K, respectively. An orthophoto showing the site location is presented in Fig. 2c.

Cesium Reference Site–Černé Údolí

The reference site is located in an area with relatively high residual ^{137}Cs surface activity. The average ^{137}Cs surface activity, determined via field gamma spectrometry, is 9.3 kBq/m². Average concentrations of natural radionuclides are 1.13 % K, 3.1 ppm eU, and 9.5 ppm eTh.

The elevated ^{137}Cs concentration, together with low concentrations of natural radionuclides, creates challenging conditions for spectrometer energy stabilization algorithms that rely on natural background. Analyses of cesium in depth profiles indicate that the site meets the requirement of long-term stability since 1986 and has not been cultivated or otherwise disturbed. An orthophoto showing the site location is presented in Fig. 2d.

Background Measurement on a Water Surface

If desired, background measurements can be conducted on the Lipno water reservoir.

Figure 1: Overview map showing the locations of the reference sites in the Czech Republic

Figure 2: Locations and orthophotos of reference sites.